

CETAF Marketplace Architecture & Deployment

Taxonomic Expertise and Services Marketplace pilot

**A hive for finding and supplying
taxonomic expertise and services**

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Technical Design

The CETAF Marketplace pilot is developed by Naturalis Biodiversity Center in collaboration with other beneficiaries under the EC Funded TETTRIs project. The design for the marketplace is based upon an iterative process of collecting user stories and feedback from the TETTRIs community. This entire process is described in the [Design Document](#). The process resulted in a set of design specifications which from the most urgent ones were converted into a fully interactive [prototype](#).

After some discussion it was decided to host the application internally within CETAF. Design specifications were updated to support this. The design specifications are listed in Table 1, where we use the MoSCoW¹ prioritisation method to indicate *if a design specification is a must, should, could or would have*. Prioritisation that was altered or became obsolete during the consultation process with stakeholders is indicated as "altered" and "obsolete".

Design specification	MoSCoW
DS1: The CETAF logo will be visible at all times in the header component.	Must
DS2: The Marketplace will receive its own name and subtitle which can be used in the header component to present its identity.	Must
DS3: The Marketplaces' homepage needs a catchy slogan that will be big and prominent so it is the first thing users will see.	Must
DS4: The Marketplace will include a footer component providing information about the funding for TETTRIs, privacy policy and terms and conditions of CETAF.	Must
DS5: The Marketplace will be marketed, physically be hosted and virtually be accessible via the CETAF server/domain.	Must (altered)
DS6: The Marketplace will serve an about page so unaffiliated users can learn about the concept of taxonomy and the Marketplaces' purpose.	Should
DS7: Users of the Marketplace will be able to create an account with ORCID and define their taxonomic profile.	Obsolete

¹ MoSCoW - A prioritization technique used to reach a common understanding with stakeholders on the importance they place on the delivery of each requirement.

DS8: Users will be able to find other users in the Marketplace and interact with them via annotations functionality.	Obsolete
DS9: CETAF admins are able to add new, edit or remove existing taxonomic services (CRUD actions) via the Cordra software.	Must (altered)
DS10: Users with the role of CETAF admin will be able to review suggested services by other users in the DiSSCo/CETAF Helpdesk, either accepting or denying them.	Must (altered)
DS11: The Cordra software provides an elegant, but simple admin interface to monitor the Marketplaces' contents.	Must (altered)
DS12: Users will be able to suggest new taxonomic services after logging into the DiSSCo/CETAF Helpdesk using an internal form or compatible metadata source.	Must (altered)
DS13: Logged in users can request new services from the taxonomic community if they lack in the Marketplace.	Obsolete
DS14: Users with the role of CETAF admin should regularly check and review if services with a low quality rate are still sustainable for use.	Must
DS15: Users with the role of CETAF admin should get a periodic notification to check the quality of services within the Marketplace.	Obsolete
DS16: The Marketplace provides a quality indicator bar which displays the rating score of a taxonomic service.	Should
DS17: Taxonomic services created will be stored as FAIR Digital Objects, adhering to its principles.	Must (altered)
DS18: The Marketplace will contain a detailed page of each taxonomic service providing: where it can be found, how it can be accessed, why it is interoperable and how to reuse it.	Must
DS19: Before the launch of the Marketplace, the catalogue will be filled with a limited set of high quality flagship services.	Must
DS20: Logged in users will be able to rate services they have used using annotations, leaving a quality score based upon a scale.	Obsolete

DS21: Users will be able to search through the taxonomic services catalogue by providing a free text query on which results are returned.	Must
DS22: The Marketplaces' homepage will offer a quick search option so users can search for taxonomic services from the get go.	Must
DS23: Users will be able to use search filters, based on primary attributes of the data model, to refine search results.	Must
DS24: The Marketplace makes a distinction between three different search categories: taxonomic services, reference collections and taxonomic expertise; affecting the search and detail pages by dynamically changing content to fit.	Must
DS25: The Marketplace displays the count of taxonomic services, reference collections and taxonomic expertise in such a way the number is prominently displayed, but can also grow.	Should
DS26: The Marketplace provides a feed of recently added taxonomic services on the homepage.	Could
DS27: The Marketplace represents the different search categories of taxonomic services, reference collections and taxonomic expertise with easy to understand, relevant shapes.	Could
DS28: The Marketplace offers more than relevant information on the detail page like: a usefulness or current state, an uptime checker or citations.	Won't
DS29: On release, the Taxacom mailing list will be utilised to promote the Marketplace under the taxonomic community.	Should
DS30: The Marketplace will be registered as a catalogue service in the EOSC Marketplace to identify with an already existing and popular platform.	Must

Table 1: Design specifications prioritised using MoSCoW

Marketplace Architecture

Architectural design choices were [documented](#) during the development process to keep track of changes in technology and design choices. The implemented architecture is shortly described in this chapter. The marketplace developed includes both a back-end application for saving and providing data, and a front-end application (website) where users can interact with the data.

Back-end

As described in the design specifications, the marketplace needs to be able to save and provide taxonomic services. The classic CRUD actions (create, read, update and delete) fulfil these requirements. The Cordra software has been implemented as the technical solution to provide these CRUD actions and to support FAIR Digital Object (FDO) compliance, a requirement from the TETTRIs technical description.

[Cordra](#) is an open source software package provided by the Corporation for National Research Initiatives (CNRI), based in the US. CNRI engages in technology demonstration projects to further the design and implementation of new computing- and communications-based applications and operates the global [Handle System](#) infrastructure that serves Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). Cordra provides a digital object store which can be interacted with. The digital object store maintains persistent identifiers using a local Handle server which interacts with a global Handle server that is hosted externally. A requirement for digital objects to be FAIR is to have a persistent identifier. In Cordra the digital objects receive a Handle as identifier, which uses a custom prefix to ensure global uniqueness. A prefix needs to be purchased from CNRI (\$100USD for one year). The prefix allotted for the marketplace is Handle.Net prefix 20.500.14547. The purchase **will need to be renewed after 1 year**.

The document store within Cordra allows for creation, read, modification and deletion of the digital objects. It provides a DOIP API that uses the HTTPS protocol to deliver responses. With these capabilities, Cordra meets the requirements to function as the back-end application for the marketplace.

Front-end

The front-end was developed with React, a widely used and popular framework.

React is not a real framework, but rather a highly customizable wrapper written in JavaScript that is highly interactive. Internal state and access to many dependencies give it almost unlimited capabilities. This allows for the use of predefined templates for often used components like: forms, buttons and tables, and creating custom components where necessary. Besides, it is easy to deploy and has met expectations in other projects in which Naturalis is involved, like DiSSCo.

Data model

A custom data model has been adapted for the taxonomic e-services. This model, developed and reviewed by the community surrounding TETTRIs task 3.1, fits the purpose of describing a taxonomic service, while maintaining simplicity and serenity. The model is heavily based on the B. v4.00 EOSC Resource Profile (*Sanchez et al., 2022*), and reuses its terms as much as possible. Custom terms were defined under a namespace called: 'cetaf'. Another few terms are based upon other existing schemas.

The data model is constructed using the [JSON-API](#) standard. Namespaces used are:

- **erp**: EOSC resource profile namespace
- **ods**: Open Digital Specimen namespace
- **dcterms**: Dublin Core Terms namespace
- **cetaf**: CETAF custom namespace

The implemented terms are listed below:

Term	Description	Type	Required
@id	The unique identifier (Handle) of the Taxonomic Service object	String	Y
@type	A registered FDO (Fair Digital Object) type describing the service (Handle to a PID registry)	String	Y
schema:dateCreated	The date on which the Taxonomic Service was created or the item was added to a DataFeed.	Datetime	Y
schema:dateModified	The date on which the Taxonomic Service was most recently modified or	Datetime	Y

	when the item's entry was modified within a DataFeed.		
schema:status	The current state ('proposed' / 'accepted' / 'rejected') of the service	String	Y
schema:licence	A link to a machine readable licence of the service at SPDX (URL)	String	
schema::availableLanguage	A list of languages which are supported by the service IETF BCP 47 standard (ISO 639-1 2-letter language code or ISO 639-2 3-letter language code)	Array of strings	
schema:version	The version of the Service embodied by a specified resource.	String	
ods:topicDiscipline	The topic discipline relevant to the taxonomic range of the service	String	
schema:taxonomicRange	The taxonomic grouping of the organism.	Array of strings	
schema:geographicArea	The geographic area associated with the service.	String	
schema:documentation	URL to further documentation describing the service in more detail.	String	
schema:ratingValue	The rating for the content on a scale from 0 to 100	Number	
schema:ratingExplanation	A short explanation (e.g. one to two sentences) providing background context and other information that led to the conclusion expressed in the rating.	String	
schema:Service	A service provided by an organisation, e.g. delivery service, print services, etc.	Object	Y
schema:serviceType	A type that defines the kind of taxonomic service	String	Y
schema:name	The preferred name of the service (can be in any language)	String	Y
schema:description	A description of the service (english)	Text	Y
schema:slogan	A slogan or motto associated with the Service (english).	String	Y

schema:logo	An associated logo URL.	String	
schema:dateModified	The date on which the Service was most recently modified or when the item's entry was modified within a DataFeed.	Datetime	
schema:termsOfService	Human-readable terms of service documentation.	String	
schema:ContactPoint	A contact point—for example, a Customer Complaints department.	Object	
schema:email	Email address of the contact point.	String	
schema:url	URL of the item that leads to the point of contact	String	
schema:sameAs	URL of a reference Web page that unambiguously indicates the item's identity. E.g. the URL of the item's Wikipedia page, Wikidata entry, or official website.	String	
schema:Maintainer	An array of maintainers of a Dataset, software package (SoftwareApplication), or other Project. A maintainer is a Person or Organization that manages contributions to, and/or publication of, some (typically complex) artefact.	Array of objects	
schema:identifier	A unique identifier to identify the maintainer; ORCID or Wikidata identifiers are valid	String	
schema:name	Full name of the maintainer	String	
schema:Organization	The organisation the maintainer is affiliated with	Object	
schema:identifier	The ROR identifier of the organisation.	String	
schema:legalName	The official name of the organization, e.g. the registered company name.	String	
schema:FundingScheme	A FundingScheme combines organizational, project and policy aspects of grant-based funding that sets guidelines, principles and mechanisms to support other kinds of projects and activities.	Object	

schema:url	URL to webpage with the supported payment models and restrictions that apply to the Resource.	String	
schema:Funder	A person or organization that supports (sponsors) something through some kind of financial contribution.	Object	
schema:name	The name of the funder (funding program)	String	
schema:SoftwareSourceCode	Object representing the service's software source code	Object	
schema:codeRepository	Link to the repository where the un-compiled, human readable code and related code is located (SVN, GitHub, CodePlex).	String	
schema:about	The subject matter of the content including a summary of the Resource features updated from the previous version.	String	
schema:runtimePlatform	Runtime platform or script interpreter dependencies (example: Java v1, Python 2.3, .NET Framework 3.0).	String	
schema:creativeWorkStatus	The status of a creative work in terms of its stage in a lifecycle. Example terms include Incomplete, Draft, Published, Obsolete. Some organizations define a set of terms for the stages of their publication lifecycle.	String	
schema:programmingLanguage	The computer programming language.	String	
schema:license	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	String	
schema:AssociatedMedia	Array of media objects that encodes this Service. This property is a synonym for encoding.	Array of objects	
schema:contentUrl	Actual bytes of the media object, for example the image file or video file.	String	
schema:license	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL	String	

Table 2: Taxonomic service data model

schema:serviceType vocabulary:

- Reference collection
- AI training dataset
- Data tool
- Identification
- Crowd sourcing
- e-Learning service
- Inventory
- Specimen dataset not in GBIF
- Community group
- Website
- Factsheet

Deployment

The TETTRIs Marketplace is bundled into a singular package that can be deployed on a web server that supports Docker and Docker Compose. The package consists of a Docker Compose file for booting the applications, configuration file for Cordra's credentials and a configuration file for NGINX.

The following paragraphs describe the steps for deploying and configuring the TETTRIs Marketplace software.

Prerequisite: Docker and Docker Compose need to be installed.

Step 1: Get the deployment package onto the server

Download the deployment package from [GitHub](#). Copy the contents of the package onto your server.

To get the deployment package: copy the contents from the downloaded package onto your server.

Step 2: Cordra configuration

The deployment package contains a folder called: 'Cordra'. In this folder, a file called: 'variables.env' contains all the variables used in the Cordra instance. This includes the credentials for the admin user.

To configure Cordra: Fill in values for the admin credentials in the variables file and save the changes (see image below).

```
# (REQUIRED) - password for the admin user
CORDRA_ADMIN_PASS=password
# Base uri for this Cordra instance
CORDRA_BASE_URI=/cordra
# Handle prefix to use
CORDRA_PREFIX=20.500.14547.
# Handle admin for the above prefix
CORDRA_HDL_ADMIN=20.500.14547/repo
```

Image 1: Example variables.env file

Step 3: NGINX and Certbot configuration

NGINX is a router that will receive requests from the user and based upon a route redirects the user to the correct service, being it the front- or back-end. Certbot is used to request SSL certificates for the domain to execute a hand shake with the user's browser, validating the web site.

In order to configure NGINX and Certbot, it is mandatory to enter the URL you will be running the marketplace on into the `nginx.conf` file. The default url is: `marketplace.cetaf.org`. If you are running the marketplace on a different domain, make sure to replace the string: `marketplace.cetaf.org`, with your URL on all occurrences in the `nginx.conf` file. Save the file afterwards.

To configure NGINX and Certbot: Enter or replace the `marketplace.cetaf.org` string in the `nginx.conf` file with the base url of the domain you will be running the marketplace on.

Step 4: Docker Compose

Docker Compose is used to deploy four individual applications that together form the TETTRIs Marketplace. The applications include: the front-end, back-end, NGINX and Certbot. Make sure Docker and Docker Compose are already installed on the machine that is being used.

To deploy the applications using Docker Compose: Navigate into the deployment folder where you copied the deployment package's contents and check if the `Docker-Compose.yaml` file is present. If so, execute the following commands:

`docker-compose pull` Which will pull all the images needed to boot the applications.

`docker-compose up -d` Which will build and deploy the downloaded images into containers
and create a network between them.

This should set up all the applications. Test if you are able to see the marketplace by navigating to your host url. The base url hosts the front-end. Cordra is hosted on the `/cordra` route. So to access Cordra, navigate to: `base-url/cordra`.

If the application is not booting, you can check the running applications by executing:

`docker-compose ps -a` To check which applications are running.

If one of the applications is not working according to the summary `docker-compose ps -a` gives, try reading the logs of it by executing:

`docker-compose logs ~name of container~` To check the logs of the given container.

To shut down the applications, use the command:

`docker-compose down` To shut down all the applications in the network.

For further support with Docker Compose commands, please refer to the [documentation](#).

References

Sanchez et al. (12-14-2022) *B. v4.00 EOSC Resource Profile*.

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/B.+v4.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile>